

**Studies on Some Less-familiar Ferrocyanogen Complexes.
Part XVIII. Potentiometric and Conductometric
Studies on Manganese(III) Complexes**

Wahid U. Malik, R. P. Agarwal, and S. K. Verma

Direct and reverse titrations between manganic sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide have been carried out by conductometric and potentiometric methods. Reverse conductometric titrations (manganic sulphate solution in the cell) could not be carried out due to very high conductance of the solution. The most of the titrations provide a molar ratio 1:1, showing thereby that $Mn(III)$ can be precisely determined against potassium ferrocyanide. Evidence for the existence of the complexes $Mn^{III}FeCyg$ and $KMn^{III}Fe^{II}Cyg$ has been obtained on the basis of these titrations.

In view of the recent amperometric studies¹ on the interaction of $Mn(III)$ and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and the possible existence of redox potential in the reacting species involved in the reaction, it was considered worthwhile to investigate the reaction more extensively, employing other physico-chemical methods. In this communication, results of the potentiometric and conductometric titrations between $Mn(III)$ and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ are reported. Studies have been carried out both with manganic sulphate and manganic pyrophosphate in view of the lesser stability of the sulphate solutions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The solution of manganic sulphate was obtained by Ubbelohde's method² with the modification of adding double the amount of H_2SO_4 to ensure maximum stability. A stock solution of sodium manganic pyrophosphate was prepared by the method described by Drummond and Waters³ and Belohev and West⁴. These solutions were standardised potentiometrically against standard ferrous ammonium sulphate. Reagent grade potassium ferrocyanide (B.D.H.) was dissolved in oxygen-free conductivity water and standardised volumetrically against potassium permanganate⁵.

Potentiometric measurements were carried out by a Pye Precision Vernier Potentiometer (Cat. No. 7568); bright platinum and S.C.E. served as indicator and reference electrodes, respectively. Pye Conductivity Bridge (Cat. No. 7401) was used for conductometric measurements. Direct (Mn^{3+} in the cell) as well as reverse [$K_4Fe(CN)_6$ in the cell] titrations were carried out at various concentrations of Mn^{3+} and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solutions.

1. Malik, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 301.

2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1805.

3. *Ibid.*, 1953, 435, 440, 2836, 3119; 1955, 497.

4. *Anal. Chem. Acta*, 1952, 8, 322.

5. Sulten, "Volumetric Analysis", 10th ed., p. 217.

6. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., p. 281.

Results of the potentiometric titrations of Mn(III) sulphate and pyrophosphate (10 ml) solutions are recorded in Tables I and II (Fig. 1 and 2) respectively. Similar data for reverse titrations are included in Tables III and IV (Fig. 3 and 4).

TABLE I

Mn(III) sulphate.	$K_4Fe(CN)_6$.	Molar ratio at inflection point.
$5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$	$5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$	1 : 1 (Fig. 1, curve 1)
4.0×10^{-3}	6.6×10^{-3}	1 : 1 (Fig. 1, curve 2)
2.5×10^{-3}	6.6×10^{-3}	1 : 1 (Fig. 1, curve 3)

TABLE II

Mn(III) pyrophosphate.	$H_2SO_4(4N)$.	$K_4Fe(CN)_6$.	Molar ratio at inflection point.
$4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$	2 ml	$4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$	1 : 1 (Fig. 2, curve 1)
1.00×10^{-3}	2	1.00×10^{-3}	1 : 1 (Fig. 2, curve 2)
2.50×10^{-3}	2	2.50×10^{-3}	1 : 1 (Fig. 2, curve 3)
1.43×10^{-3}	2	1.43×10^{-3}	1 : 1 (Fig. 2, curve 4)
1.00×10^{-3}	2	1.00×10^{-3}	1 : 1 (Fig. 2, curve 5)

TABLE III

$K_4Fe(CN)_6$.	Mn(III) sulphate.	Molar ratio at inflection point.
$5.00 \times 10^{-3} M$	$4.6 \times 10^{-3} M$	1:0.72, 1 : 1 (Fig. 3, curve 1)
2.50×10^{-3}	"	1 : 0.68, 1 : 1 (Fig. 3, curve 2)
1.25×10^{-3}	"	1 : 0.71, 1 : 1 (Fig. 3, curve 3)

TABLE IV

$K_4Fe(CN)_6$.	Conn. & vol. of H_2SO_4 .	Mn(III) pyrophosphate.	Molar ratio at inflection point.
$4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$	0.0 ml (4N)	$4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$	No inflection
"	0.5 (4N)	"	1 : 0.53, 1 : 1 (Fig. 4, curve 1)
"	1.0 (4N)	"	1 : 0.55, 1 : 1 (Fig. 4, curve 2)
"	2.0 (4N)	"	1 : 0.55, 1 : 1 (Fig. 4, curve 3)
"	10.0 (12N)	"	1 : 1 (Fig. 4, curve 4)
1.00×10^{-3}	2.0 (4N)	$1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$	1 : 1 (Fig. 4, curve 5)
"	10.0 (12N)	"	1 : 1 (Fig. 4, curve 6)
2.50×10^{-3}	2.0 (4N)	2.50×10^{-3}	1 : 1 (Fig. 4, curve 7)
1.43×10^{-3}	"	1.43×10^{-3}	1 : 1 (Fig. 4, curve 8)
1.00×10^{-3}	"	1.00×10^{-3}	1 : 1 (Fig. 4, curve 9)

Both direct and reverse conductometric titrations were carried out between manganese pyrophosphate and potassium ferrocyanide solutions. The results are shown in Fig. 5 and 6, respectively. A combining ratio, $Mn(III): Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$, as 1 : 1 was obtained here also.

DISCUSSION

From Fig. 1 and 2, it is evident that the values of ΔE at inflection points in case of $Mn(III)$ sulphate are fairly large as compared to those in $Mn(III)$ pyrophosphate titrations. This behaviour is quite normal in view of the oxidation potentials of the two reagents, -1.51 V and -1.15 V, respectively. In $Mn(III)$ pyrophosphate titrations (Fig. 2, 4, 5 & 6) addition of a little sulphuric acid was found to be essential due to instability of $Mn(III)$ pyrophosphate solutions in alkaline medium. Moreover, oxidation proceeded smoothly below a pH of about 2.5. In the direct titrations (Fig. 1 & 2) a sharp inflection always appeared at a molar ratio of 1 : 1 (Tables I & II) indicating the reaction:

FIG. 1. Potentiometric titrations of $Mn(III)$ sulphate. Curve 1: $Mn(III)$ ($8 \times 10^{-2}M$), K_4FeCyg ($6 \times 10^{-2}M$). Curve 2: $Mn(III)$ ($4 \times 10^{-2}M$), K_4FeCyg ($6.6 \times 10^{-2}M$). Curve 3: $Mn(III)$ ($2.5 \times 10^{-2}M$), K_4FeCyg ($6.6 \times 10^{-2}M$).

FIG. 2. Potentiometric titrations of $Mn(III)$ pyrophosphate in presence of H_2SO_4 (2 ml, $4N$): 1: $1.4 \times 10^{-2}M$; 2: $2.1 \times 10^{-2}M$; 3: $2.5 \times 10^{-2}M$; 4: $1.43 \times 10^{-2}M$; 5: $5.1 \times 10^{-2}M$ in $Mn(III)$ pyrophosphate. Concentrations of K_4FeCyg same as given for $Mn(III)$ pyrophosphate.

Nature of the first-half portion of the curves 1, 2, and 3 (Fig. 4) for the potentiometric titrations of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ ($4 \times 10^{-2}M$) in presence of 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 ml of $4N-H_2SO_4$ with $Mn(III)$ pyrophosphate is different from the other curves obtained with dilute solutions titrated under exactly similar conditions (Table IV). Here another inflection, although

not well defined, appeared corresponding to the interaction of one half mole of Mn(III) and one mole of potassium ferrocyanide. The colour of the precipitate up to this point remained yellow and then changed to brown on further addition of Mn(III) pyrophosphate. This ratio was not, however, arrived at when titrations with manganic sulphate were carried out (Table III, Fig. 3) although the colour of the precipitate before the first inflection point was yellow as in the case of Mn(III) pyrophosphate product corresponding to the first inflection point. Here the molar ratio of Mn(III) to $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ appeared as 0.7:1.

FIG. 3. Potentiometric titrations of K_4FeCy_6 with Mn(III) sulphate ($4.0 \times 10^{-2} M$).

Curve 1: $5 \times 10^{-2} M$.

Curve 2: $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$.

Curve 3: $1.25 \times 10^{-2} M$ in K_4FeCy_6 .

FIG. 4. Potentiometric titrations of K_4FeCy_6 with Mn(III) pyrophosphate in presence of H_2SO_4 .

Curves 1-3: $4 \times 10^{-2} M$ in K_4FeCy_6 in presence of 0.5, 1.0 & 2 ml respectively of H_2SO_4 (4*N*). Curve 4 same as 1-3 but in presence of 10 ml H_2SO_4 (12*N*). Curves 5, 7, 8 & 9: $1 \times 10^{-2} M$, $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $1.43 \times 10^{-3} M$ & $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ respectively in K_4FeCy_6 in presence of 2 ml H_2SO_4 (4*N*). Curves 6 same as 5 but in presence of 10 ml H_2SO_4 (12*N*). Concentrations of Mn(III) pyrophosphate same as given for K_4FeCy_6 . Origin A for curves 3, 5, 6 & 8. Origin B for curves 1, 2, 4, 7 & 9.

The above facts appear to suggest that the reaction occurs probably in the following two steps at high ferrocyanide concentration and low acidity.

Curve 4 (Fig. 4) for the potentiometric titration of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ ($4 \times 10^{-2} M$) in presence of a fairly large excess of sulphuric acid does not exhibit two inflections. Only one inflection point, corresponding to the formation of 1:1 complex, is realised. Similar behaviour was observed on employing dilute solutions of potassium ferrocyanide and manga-

nic pyrophosphate, even with low acid content of the reaction mixtures (curves 5 to 9, Fig. 4).

The potentiometric method, described above, may be advantageously employed for the estimation of Mn(III) in very dilute solutions. Direct titrations, carried out even with solutions as dilute as $10^{-3}M$, exhibit sharp inflections, almost of the same order as with $4 \times 10^{-2}M$ solutions. Reverse titrations, however, did not provide satisfactory results (change in potential at the inflection for $10^{-3}M$ solution = 60 mV) in dilute solutions and hence cannot be employed for the estimation of Mn(III) solutions of fairly low concentrations.

FIG. 5. Conductometric titrations of Mn(III) pyrophosphate (20ml) with K_4FeCyg ($4 \times 10^{-2}M$) in presence of H_2SO_4 (2ml, 4*N*.):
1: $2 \times 10^{-2}M$; 2: $10 \times 10^{-2}M$; 3: $2.5 \times 10^{-2}M$
in Mn(III) pyrophosphate.

FIG. 6. Conductometric titrations of K_4FeCyg (20 ml) with Mn(III) pyrophosphate ($4 \times 10^{-2}M$) in presence of H_2SO_4 (2 ml, 4*N*.):
1: $1 \times 10^{-2}M$; 2: $3 \times 10^{-2}M$;
3: $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ in K_4FeCyg .

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